

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 107

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 107

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 107:1 Oh ^agive thanks to the LORD, for ^bHe is good, For His lovingkindness is everlasting. ² Let ^athe redeemed of the LORD say so, Whom He has ^bredeemed from the hand of the adversary ³ And ^agathered from the lands, From the east and from the west, From the north and from the ¹south.</p> <p>Psa. 107:4 They ^awandered in the wilderness in a ¹desert region; They did not find a way to ²an inhabited ^bcity. ⁵ They were hungry ¹and thirsty; Their ^asoul fainted within them. ⁶ Then they ^acried out to the LORD in their trouble; He delivered them out of their distresses. ⁷ He led them also by a ^{1a}straight way, To go to ^{2b}an inhabited city. ⁸ ^aLet them give thanks to the LORD for His lovingkindness, And for His ¹wonders to the sons of men! ⁹ For He has ^asatisfied the ¹thirsty soul, And the ^bhungry soul He has filled with what is good.</p>	<p>Psa. 107:1 לְעוֹלָם תְּסַדְּרוּ : ² יֹאמְרוּ גְּאוּלַי יְהוָה אֲשֶׁר גָּאֲלָם מִיַּד-צָר : ³ וּמֵאֲרָצוֹת קְבָצָם מִמִּזְרַח וּמִמְּעַרְב מִצָּפוֹן וּמִמִּזְרָח : ⁴ תָּעוּ בַמִּדְבָּר בִּישִׁימוֹן דֶּרֶךְ עֵיר מוֹשֵׁב לֹא מָצְאוּ : ⁵ רָעֵבִים גַּם-צָמְאִים נַפְשָׁם בָּהֶם תִּתְעַטֵּף : ⁶ וַיִּזְעַקוּ אֶל-יְהוָה בַּצָּר לָהֶם מִמִּצְוִקוֹתֵיהֶם יִצִּילֵם : ⁷ וַיַּדְרִיכֵם בְּדֶרֶךְ יִשְׂרָאֵל לְלֶכֶת אֶל- עֵיר מוֹשֵׁב : ⁸ יוֹדוּ לַיהוָה תְּסַדְּרוּ וְנִבְלְאוּתֵי לִבֵּי אָדָם : ⁹ כִּי- הִשְׁבִּיעַ נַפֶּשׁ שִׁקְקָה וְנַפֶּשׁ רָעֵבָה מִלֵּא-טוֹב : ¹⁰ יִשְׁבִּי תַשְׁדֵּךְ וְצַלְמוֹת אֲסִירֵי עֲנִי וּבְרִזָּל : ¹¹ כִּי-הִמְרוּ אֲמָרֵי-אֵל וַעֲצַת עֲלִיוֹן נֶאֱצַו : ¹² וַיִּכְנַע בְּעַמְל לָבָם כִּשְׁלוֹ וְאִין עִזָּר : ¹³ וַיִּזְעַקוּ אֶל-יְהוָה בַּצָּר לָהֶם מִמִּצְוִקוֹתֵיהֶם יוֹשִׁיעֵם : ¹⁴ יוֹצִיאֵם מִתַּשְׁדֵּךְ וְצַלְמוֹת וּמוֹסְרוֹתֵיהֶם יִנְתַּק : ¹⁵ יוֹדוּ לַיהוָה תְּסַדְּרוּ וְנִבְלְאוּתֵי לִבֵּי אָדָם : ¹⁶ כִּי-שָׂבַר דַּלְתוֹת נְחֹשֶׁת וּבְרִיחֵי בְרִזָּל גִּדְּעַ : ¹⁷ אֲוִלִים מִדֶּרֶךְ פִּשְׁעֵם וּמַעֲוֹנוֹתֵיהֶם</p>

Psa. 107:10 There were those who dwelt in darkness and in the shadow of death,

^bPrisoners in ¹misery and ²chains,

¹¹ Because they had rebelled against the words of God

And ^bspurned the counsel of the Most High.

¹² Therefore He humbled their heart with labor;

They stumbled and there was none to help.

¹³ Then they cried out to the LORD in their trouble;

He saved them out of their distresses.

¹⁴ He brought them out of darkness and the shadow of death

And ^bbroke their bands apart.

¹⁵ Let them give thanks to the LORD for His lovingkindness,

And for His wonders to the sons of men!

¹⁶ For He has shattered gates of bronze

And cut bars of iron asunder.

Psa. 107:17 Fools, because of their rebellious way,

And because of their iniquities, were afflicted.

¹⁸ Their soul abhorred all kinds of food,

And they drew near to the gates of death.

¹⁹ Then they cried out to the LORD in their trouble;

He saved them out of their distresses.

²⁰ He sent His word and healed them,

יִתְעַנּוּ : כָּל־אֶכֶל תִּתְעַב נַפְשָׁם ¹⁸

וַיִּזְעֻקוּ עַד־שְׁעַר מוֹת : וַיִּזְעֻקוּ ¹⁹

אֶל־יְהוָה בְּצַר לָהֶם מִמְצַקוֹתֵיהֶם

יּוֹשִׁיעֵם : יִשְׁלַח דְּבָרוֹ וַיִּרְפָּאֵם ²⁰

וַיִּמְלֹט מִשְׁחִיתוֹתָם : וְיִדְרוּ ²¹

לִיהוָה תַסְדִּי וַנִּבְלָאוּתִי לִבְנֵי

אָדָם : וַיִּזְבַּחוּ זִבְחֵי תוֹרָה ²²

וַיִּסְפְּרוּ מַעֲשָׂיו בְּרִנָּה : וְיִזְרְיֵי ²³

הַיָּם בְּאֲנִיּוֹת עֲשֵׂי מְלָאכָה בְּמַיִם

רַבִּים : וְיִתְפַּח רֹאשׁוֹ מִעֲשֵׂי יְהוָה ²⁴

וַנִּבְלָאוּתִי בְּמִצּוֹלָה : וַיִּיאָמֶר ²⁵

וַיֵּעֲמֵד רוּחַ סְעָרָה וַתְּרוּמֵם גִּלְיוֹ : וְ

יַעֲלוּ שָׁמַיִם יִרְדּוּ תְּהוֹמוֹת נַפְשָׁם ²⁶

בְּרַעַה תִּתְמוּגַג : יִחַוְגוּ וַיִּנּוּעוּ ²⁷

כַּשָּׂכּוֹר וְכָל־חֲכָמָתָם תִּתְבַּלַּע : ²⁸

וַיִּזְעֻקוּ אֶל־יְהוָה בְּצַר לָהֶם

וַמִּמְצַוֹקֹתֵיהֶם יוֹצִיאֵם : יִקַּם ²⁹

סְעָרָה לְדָמָמָה וַיִּחַשּׁוּ גִלְיָהֶם : ³⁰

וַיִּשְׁמְחוּ כִי־יִשְׁתַּקּוּ וַיִּנְחֵם אֶל־מַחֲזוּ

תְּפֻצָּם : יִדְרוּ לִיהוָה תַסְדִּי ³¹

וַנִּבְלָאוּתִי לִבְנֵי אָדָם : ³²

וַיִּרְמְמוּהוּ בְּקֶהֱל־עַם וּבְמוֹשֵׁב

זָקֵנִים יִתְלַלְּוהוּ : יִשֶׁם נְהַרְרוֹת ³³

לְמִדְבָּר וּמִצְאֵי מַיִם לְצִמְאֹן : ³⁴

אֶרֶץ פָּרִי לְמִלְחָה מְרַעַת יִשְׁבֵי

בָּהּ : יִשֶׁם מִדְבָּר לְאִגַּם־מַיִם ³⁵

וְאֶרֶץ צִיָּה לְמִצְאֵי מַיִם : וַיִּוֹשֵׁב ³⁶

שָׁם רַעֲבִים וַיְכֹנְנוּ עֵיר מוֹשָׁב : ³⁷

And ^cdelivered *them* from their
¹destructions.

²¹ ^aLet them give thanks to the
LORD for His lovingkindness,

And for His ¹wonders to the sons
of men!

²² Let them also offer ^asacrifices of
thanksgiving,

And ^btell of His works with joyful
singing.

Psa. 107:23 Those who ^ago down
to the sea in ships,

Who do business on great waters;

²⁴ They have seen the works of the
LORD,

And His ¹wonders in the deep.

²⁵ For He ^aspoke and raised up a
^bstormy wind,

Which ^clifted up the waves ¹of the
sea.

²⁶ They rose up to the heavens, they
went down to the depths;

Their soul ^amelted away in *their*
misery.

²⁷ They reeled and ^astaggered like a
drunken man,

And ¹were at their wits' end.

²⁸ Then they cried to the LORD in
their trouble,

And He brought them out of their
distresses.

²⁹ He ^acaused the storm to be still,
So that the waves ¹of the sea were
hushed.

³⁰ Then they were glad because they
were quiet,

So He guided them to their desired
haven.

³¹ ^aLet them give thanks to the
LORD for His lovingkindness,

וַיִּזְרְעוּ שָׂדוֹת וַיִּטְעוּ כְּרָמִים וַיִּעֲשׂוּ

פְּרֵי תְבוּאָה : ³⁸ וַיְבָרְכֶם וַיִּרְבּוּ

מְאֹד וּבְהַמְתֶּם לֹא יִמְעִיט : ³⁹

וַיִּמְעֲטוּ וַיִּשְׁחוּ מֵעֶצֶר רָעָה וַיִּגְזוּ : וְ

⁴⁰ שִׁפְךָ בַיָּם עַל־נְדִיבִים וַיִּתְעַם

בְּתֵהוּ לֹא־דָרַךְ : ⁴¹ וַיִּשְׁגַּב אֲבִיוֹן

מֵעוֹנֵי וַיִּשֶׁם כַּצֹּאן מִשְׁפָּחוֹת : ⁴²

יִרְאוּ יִשְׂרָאֵל וַיִּשְׁמְחוּ וְכָל־עוֹלָה

קִבְּצָה פִּיהָ : ⁴³ מִי־חֲכָם וַיִּשְׁמְד־

אֱלֹהֵהּ וַיִּתְבּוֹנְנוּ תַסְדֵי יְהוָה :

And for His ^{1b}wonders to the sons
of men!

³² Let them ^aextol Him also ^bin the
congregation of the people,

And ^cpraise Him at the seat of the
elders.

Psa. 107:33 He ^{1a}changes rivers
into a ²wilderness

And springs of water into a thirsty
ground;

³⁴ A ^afruitful land into a ^bsalt waste,
Because of the wickedness of
those who dwell in it.

³⁵ He ^{1a}changes a ²wilderness into a
pool of water

And a dry land into springs of
water;

³⁶ And there He makes the hungry to
dwell,

So that they may establish ^{1a}an
inhabited city,

³⁷ And sow fields and ^aplant
vineyards,

And ¹gather a fruitful harvest.

³⁸ Also He blesses them and they
^amultiply greatly,

And He ^bdoes not let their cattle
decrease.

Psa. 107:39 When they are
^adiminished and ^bbowed down

Through oppression, misery and
sorrow,

⁴⁰ He ^apours contempt upon ¹princes
And ^bmakes them wander ^cin a
pathless waste.

⁴¹ But He ^asets the needy ¹securely on
high away from affliction,

And ^bmakes *his* families like a flock.

⁴² The ^aupright see it and are glad;

<p>But all ^bunrighteousness shuts its mouth.</p> <p>⁴³ Who is ^awise? Let him give heed to these things,</p> <p>And consider the ^blovingkindnesses of the LORD.</p>	
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References

Psalm 107:1

^a1 Chr 16:34; Ps 106:1; 118:1; 136:1; Jer 33:11

^b2 Chr 5:13; 7:3; Ezra 3:11; Ps 100:5

Psalm 107:2

^aIs 35:9, 10; 62:12; 63:4

^bPs 78:42; 106:10

Psalm 107:3

¹Lit *sea*

^aDeut 30:3; Neh 1:9; Ps 106:47; Is 11:12; 43:5; 56:8; Ezek 11:17; 20:34

Psalm 107:4

¹Lit *waste*

²Or *a habitable city*; lit *a city of habitation*

^aNum 14:33; 32:13; Deut 2:7; 32:10; Josh 5:6; 14:10

^bPs 107:7, 36

Psalm 107:5

¹Lit *also*

^aPs 77:3

Psalm 107:6

^aPs 50:15; 107:13, 19, 28

Psalm 107:7

¹Or *level*

²Or *a habitable city*; lit *a city of habitation*

^aEzra 8:21; Ps 5:8; Jer 31:9

^bPs 107:4, 36

Psalm 107:8

¹I.e. wonderful acts

^aPs 107:15, 21, 31

Psalm 107:9

¹Or *parched*

^aPs 22:26; 34:10; 63:5; 103:5

^bPs 146:7; Matt 5:6; Luke 1:53

Psalm 107:10

¹Lit *affliction*

²Lit *irons*

^aPs 143:3; Is 42:7; Mic 7:8; Luke 1:79

^bJob 36:8; Ps 102:20

Psalm 107:11

^aPs 78:40; 106:7; Lam 3:42

^bNum 15:31; 2 Chr 36:16; Prov 1:25; Is 5:24

^cPs 73:24

Psalm 107:12

^aPs 22:11; 72:12

Psalm 107:13

^aPs 107:6

Psalm 107:14

^aPs 86:13; 107:10

^bPs 116:16; Jer 2:20; 30:8; Nah 1:13; Luke 13:16; Acts 12:7

Psalm 107:15

¹I.e. wonderful acts

^aPs 107:8, 21, 31

Psalm 107:16

^aIs 45:1, 2

Psalm 107:17

¹Lit *the way of their transgression*

^aIs 65:6, 7; Jer 30:14, 15; Lam 3:39; Ezek 24:23

Psalm 107:18

^aJob 33:20; Ps 102:4

^bJob 33:22; Ps 88:3

^cJob 38:17; Ps 9:13

Psalm 107:20

¹Or *pits*

^aPs 147:15, 18; Matt 8:8

^b2 Kin 20:5; Ps 30:2; 103:3; 147:3

^cJob 33:28, 30; Ps 30:3; 49:15; 56:13; 103:4

Psalm 107:21

¹I.e. wonderful acts

^aPs 107:8, 15, 31

Psalm 107:22

^aLev 7:12; Ps 50:14; 116:17

^bPs 9:11; 73:28; 118:17

Psalm 107:23

^aIs 42:10; Jon 1:3

Psalm 107:24

¹I.e. wonderful acts

Psalm 107:25

¹Lit *of it*

^aPs 105:31, 34

^bPs 148:8; Jon 1:4

^cPs 93:3, 4

Psalm 107:26

^aPs 22:14; 119:28

Psalm 107:27

¹Lit *all their wisdom was swallowed up*

^aJob 12:25; Is 24:20

Psalm 107:29

¹Lit *of it*

^aPs 65:7; 89:9; Matt 8:26; Luke 8:24

Psalm 107:31

¹I.e. wonderful acts

^aPs 107:8, 15, 21

^bPs 78:4; 111:4

Psalm 107:32

^aPs 34:3; 99:5; Is 25:1

^bPs 22:22, 25

^cPs 35:18

Psalm 107:33

¹Or *turns*

²Or *desert*

^a1 Kin 17:1, 7; Ps 74:15; Is 42:15; 50:2

Psalm 107:34

^aGen 13:10; 14:3; 19:24, 25; Deut 29:23

^bJob 39:6; Jer 17:6

Psalm 107:35

¹Or *turns*

²Or *desert*

^aPs 105:41; 114:8; Is 35:6, 7; 41:18

Psalm 107:36

¹Or *a habitable city*; lit *a city of habitation*

^aPs 107:4, 7

Psalm 107:37

¹Lit *acquire fruits of yield*

^a2 Kin 19:29; Is 65:21; Amos 9:14

Psalm 107:38

^aGen 12:2; 17:20; Ex 1:7; Deut 1:10

^bDeut 7:14

Psalm 107:39

^a2 Kin 10:32; Ezek 5:11; 29:15

^bPs 38:6; 44:25; 57:6

Psalm 107:40

¹Or *nobles*

^aJob 12:21

^bJob 12:24

^cDeut 32:10

Psalm 107:41

¹Lit *in an inaccessibly high place*

^a1 Sam 2:8; Ps 59:1; 113:7, 8

^bJob 21:11; Ps 78:52; 113:9

Psalm 107:42

^aJob 22:19; Ps 52:6

^bJob 5:16; Ps 63:11; Rom 3:19

Psalm 107:43

^aPs 64:9; Jer 9:12; Hos 14:9

^bPs 107:1

Targum

Psa. 107:1 Sing praise in the presence of the LORD, for he is good, for his goodness is forever. ² The redeemed of the LORD will say [it], whom he redeemed from the hand of the oppressor. ³ And whom he gathered from the lands, from the east, and from the west, and from the north, and from the sea in the south. ⁴ Concerning the people of the house of Israel he prophesied and said, “The people of the house of Israel have wandered in the wilderness in a desolate path; they did not find an inhabited city.” ⁵ Thirsty, yes, and hungry, their souls will grow weary. ⁶ And they prayed in the presence of the LORD when it went ill with them; he delivered them from their distress. ⁷ And he guided them on a straight way, to come to Jerusalem, the inhabited city. ⁸ Let them give thanks in the presence of the LORD because of his kindness, and tell his wonders to the sons of men. ⁹ For he has satisfied the soul of the empty, and filled with good things the soul of the hungry. ¹⁰ Concerning Zedekiah and the leaders of Israel he prophesied and said, “O Zedekiah and the leaders of Israel, who were exiled to Babylon and dwelt in darkness and the shadow of death, and became prisoners in the pain of iron fetters.” ¹¹ For they rebelled against the word of God, and rejected the counsel of the Most High. ¹² And he broke their heart with toil; they stumbled, and there was none to help. ¹³ And they prayed in the presence of the LORD when it went ill with them; he redeemed them from their distress. ¹⁴ He brought them out of darkness and the shadow of death; and he will break their chains. ¹⁵ They will give thanks in the presence of the LORD because of his kindness, and tell his wonders to the sons of men. ¹⁶ For he shattered the doors of bronze, and cut down the bars of iron. ¹⁷ Concerning Hezekiah, king of the tribe of the house of Judah, he prophesied and said, “Hezekiah, king of the house of Judah, who refused to take a wife, was punished as the fools are punished because of their rebellious way and because of their iniquities.” ¹⁸ Their soul will reject all food, and they arrive at the portals of death. ¹⁹ And they prayed in the presence of the LORD when it went ill with them, and he will redeem them from their distresses. ²⁰ He will send the words of his healing and will heal them, and deliver [them] from being harmed. ²¹ They will give thanks in the presence of the LORD because of his kindness, and tell his wonders to the sons of men. ²² And they will sacrifice thanksgiving sacrifices, and will tell of his deeds in gladness. ²³ Concerning the sailors of Jonah son of Amittai, he prophesied and said, “The sailors, those who go down to the sea in ships, those who do work on many waters – ²⁴ They saw the deeds of the LORD, and his wonders in the deep.” ²⁵ And he gave command by his word, and raised up the storm and the gale, and its waves were lifted up high. ²⁶ They go up towards heaven, they go down to the depths of the abysses; their souls will melt in misery. ²⁷ They will tremble, they will totter like a man drunk with wine; and all their wisdom is destroyed. ²⁸ And they prayed in the presence of the LORD when it went ill with them, and he will bring them out of their troubles. ²⁹ He will make the wind cease to quietness, and their waves will be silent. ³⁰ And they rejoiced, for they are silent; and he led them to the harbor they desired. ³¹ They will give thanks in the presence of the LORD because of his kindness, and tell his wonders to the sons of men. ³² And they exalt him in the assembly of the people, the house of Israel; and in the Sanhedrin of the wise they will praise him. ³³ Concerning the generation of Joel son of Pethuel he prophesied and said: “When the house of Israel rebelled in the days of Joel the prophet, he brought a drought into the world; he made the rivers like the desert, and the sources of water like thirst.” ³⁴ The land of Israel that produces fruit

became a waste like Sodom, which was overthrown because of the evil of its inhabitants. ³⁵ When they returned to the Torah, he made the desert like a channel of water, and the parched land [became] sources of water. ³⁶ And he made the hungry dwell there, and they set up an inhabited city. ³⁷ And they sowed fields and planted vineyards, and they yielded fruit of produce. ³⁸ And he blessed them and they multiplied greatly, and their livestock will not diminish. ³⁹ And when they sinned, they diminished and became poor because of the affliction of misery and pain. ⁴⁰ He pours contempt on the leaders, and made them wander in a void without a path. ⁴¹ But when they returned to the Torah, he exalted the needy from poverty, and made [them] like the flocks of the well-born families. ⁴² The upright will see and rejoice, but every liar's mouth is closed and sealed. ⁴³ Would that the wise man keep these things, and discern the kindnesses of the LORD!

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This is the first Psalm of the fifth book of Psalms. It is a composition that expresses the thanks of those who were in places of danger but were rescued and arrived home safely. The sage Ibn Yachya related this Psalm to David's life. The Philistines had captured the Ark of the Covenant, and it was endangered. David returned the Ark to a haven of safety and sanctity. This is a hymn of thanksgiving.

Notes on this Psalm

The spiritual awareness of this Psalm is the understanding that it applied in David's day and today. The Sefirah Chesed sends the LORD's lovingkindness to humanity. The LORD asks people to live by the Laws in the Torah. If one is unsure how to accomplish this, just read any of the books of the prophets and the Gospels of Jesus of Nazareth. Jesus offered the best way through his own words and actions. When a person complies with the Torah, Chesed will flow with lovingkindness. This formula is the basics of the Sinai treaty, called the Ten Commandments.

The LORD said He can protect the people who want to be part of His kingdom. One becomes a member of the domain by following the Torah. The second part of the Sinai covenant (the Ten Commandments) is following the Law. It is a simple formula that Israel has struggled with for centuries. People struggle with this concept today. The primary central theme is the same whether your religion is Judaism or Christianity. Follow the Torah; the LORD will protect you, and Chesed will send His love.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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